

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PROCESS OF BIOLOGICAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHILD

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ABSTRACT

This article is based on the results of the study of relevant literature and legal sources about the relevance of the psychophysiological characteristics of the child's healthy development, the importance of the purpose of the characteristics of the psychological development of a person in the first stages of ontogenesis.

A baby seems to us the weakest. Nevertheless, the same age is a strong point, and in this aspect, babies are superior to adults, says Professor E. A. Arkin. In his opinion, the child's strength is manifested in his growth energy. The weight of the child's body triples in the first year of life, compared to the height, a seven-month-old child grows very quickly, and at the age of eight months, the height doubles, and at the age of thirty months, it increases four times. Children grow 2 centimeters every month. His brain weight increases by 1.5 grams every day. When talking about the pace of brain development, it should be noted that the brain of a seven-month-old child doubles in size, and by the age of 2-3, its weight will increase three times. The size of the brain increases during almost 20 years, the upper "imprints" of the large hemispheres become more complex. Such a huge acceleration in the growth of children depends on the vegetative nervous system, a number of internal secretion glands (thyroid gland, etc.). The special hormones produced by the endocrine glands enter the blood and have a great impact on the growth and development of the body. The fact that babies grow so fast is a special feature of this period. Therefore, during this period, all things that affect the growth and development of the child should be good, quality food, fresh air, sufficient amount of sunlight.

The child's nervous activity is expressed in two different ways. The first of these includes unconditioned or innate reflexes, and the second includes conditioned reflexes. Unconditional reflexes are already developed by the time the child is born, as a result of which the most necessary autonomic functions, such as blood circulation, breathing and digestion, are carried out. For example, as soon as something touches the lips of a baby who has opened his stomach, there are movements indicating sucking, which is a feeding reflex, that is, an unconditioned reflex.

As mentioned above, even though the large hemispheres of the brain during birth are not developed in terms of weight, size and function, the brain is the most necessary connection between the newborn child and the external environment on the ground of

unconditional reflexes. is able to form elemental conditioned reflexes that provide the possibility of installation.

From the first days of a child's life, contact with the external environment occurs in the process of living an individual life. In the second month of a child's life, conditioned reflexes characteristic of all sensory organs are formed. But according to the researchers, the reflexes in this period of the child's life are weakly expressed and unstable.

During the growth and development of the child, the reactions become stable, appear quickly and become more differentiated.

Since conditioned reflexes appear in the child in the first months of his life, it is necessary to properly organize the upbringing of the child from the first months of his life. This prevents negative characteristics in the child's development and behavior, and ensures the normal development of the child. The increasing role of the mental departments of the central nervous system can be seen more clearly in the expression of the main nervous processes - excitation and inhibition. Braking is usually divided into two types: internal and external. The most vivid expression of internal inhibition is sleep. The external expression of inhibition is formed only due to the upbringing of the child. For this, along with the main food (for example, milk), another supplement (constantly changing the feeding bottle) affects the child. From the moment the baby is born, those around him support him in every way. They provide physical care for the child's organism, teach, educate, help to master human psychological and moral aspects, adapt to living conditions in society. Support of the child by parents and adults continues from birth until the child grows up and can lead an independent life.

From birth, babies have ready-to-use sensory and motor skills instincts that help them adapt to the world and grow rapidly in their development. Starting from birth, for example, many complex actions, mainly based on the program that was given to the organism during maturation, as well as reflex, i.e., under the influence of specific internal and external stimuli coded as the key to this program of actions. It occurs immediately after the first hours without special preparation. The period of infancy is the only period in human life in which innate, instinctive forms of behavior aimed at satisfying organic needs (for oxygen, food, heat or cold) are observed in their pure form. One of the main characteristics of children in infancy is the presence of incomparable opportunities to acquire human behavior and new experiences. As a result of adequate satisfaction of organic needs, a properly organized routine, regime and proper education, the child will have impressions that are the basis for mental development, movement, communication, and a relatively new set of needs will appear. causes it to come. From the first week of a child's birth, his senses of sight and hearing develop rapidly.

On the first day of their life, children in maternity wards instinctively turn their faces towards the window where the daylight falls.

It was found out from the conducted researches that response potentials can be seen in the brain of a one-and-a-half-day-old child to the effect of colored stimuli on the visual organ. By this time, the formation of conditioned reflexes occurs in the brain.

The sense of smell is the most important sense organ, it starts working immediately after birth. Ordinary sight, movement, and hearing have the same characteristics. In the first two months of a child's life, when the edge of the mouth is touched with an object, the reflector shows the ability to turn in response, if it is touched on the fingers, it squeezes them

tightly, makes general uncoordinated movements with its hands, legs, and head. It also has the ability to follow moving objects with its eyes and turn its head in their direction.

A baby can distinguish the taste of things. He prefers sweet liquids to the taste of other things and can even detect the level of sweetness. The baby senses smells and responds to them by turning its head, changing its heart rate and breathing rate. It is also worth mentioning that the child's organism is innately given a group of processes that help it maintain itself and develop. They are related to the management of digestion, blood circulation, breathing, body temperature, metabolic processes, etc. Undoubtedly, sucking, protective, aiming, grasping, supporting movements and a number of other reflexes are innate, all of which are clearly visible in the second month of a child's life.

The child is "directly" affected by the bright light, that is, he cannot look at the bright light and closes his eyes to it. They cannot perceive objects with their eyes, because their vision mechanism has not yet developed, these mechanisms appear at an older age. A seven- to nine-day-old child sometimes looks at a slowly moving object, but cannot look at it for a long time. Focusing on one point plays an important role in mental development. When a child is two to three months old, he can observe nearby objects with both eyes, he has the ability to distinguish basic colors and shapes. At the age of six months, he begins to express his attitude towards colors, if he strives for the color he likes, he pushes away the one he doesn't like, and turns his face away from it. A newborn baby's hearing is weaker, so he responds to very loud stimuli that he has not yet heard and accustomed to, but cannot distinguish from which direction the sound is coming. Only at the end of the second month does the child begin to pay attention to the sound it hears, looking from side to side, looking for where the sound is coming from.

It is important for the child's overall development that he listens and sees more and more carefully. But vision, hearing and other analyzers improve only as a result of the child's interaction with the environment. A child's ability to see with his own eyes is the result of certain life experiences. A child's auditory perception also learns to separate sounds and synthesize them. A child's ability to listen depends on the quality of conditional connections. A newborn does not have the ability to pay attention. It gradually develops involuntary attention under the influence of various stimuli. The smaller the scope of the child's imagination, the more intensive and continuous his attention to the familiar and new subject. The mental effect of attention is known, it transforms the sensory complex into perception, enhances the transition of mental processes and helps keep images firmly in the memory.

It is worth mentioning that the child's body is innately endowed with a group of processes that help it maintain itself and develop. They are related to the management of digestion, blood circulation, breathing, body temperature, metabolic processes, etc. Undoubtedly, sucking, protective, aiming, grasping, supporting movements and a number of other reflexes are innate, all of which are clearly visible in the second month of a child's life.

From the moment of birth, not only the child's sense organs are ready to work, but also the brain begins to work actively. Mothers should know not only the innate forms of psyche and behavior of the baby, but also the natural development process of the organism. The development of movements in the first months of life is of particular importance.

A baby's motility is sufficiently organized from birth, it includes many mechanisms designed to control situations. In the baby, high mobility activity of the limbs often appears,

which is of positive importance in the formation of a complex set of coordinated movements in the future. In babies, the arms and legs are bent, and the fingers are made into fists.

In the first months of life, when the child is restless, the movements of the arms and legs are very chaotic, uncoordinated and involuntary. Then the movements gradually become "conscious", and these movements serve as a source of new sensations, which prepare the transition to more complex movements. A 3-3.5-month-old child stretches his hands to toys, even if he does not yet have clearly coordinated movements. Precisely coordinated movement looks good in a 4-month-old child. The child can easily pick up the toy. He holds it, looks at it, touches its mouth, and in this way receives many different impressions. A two-month-old child starts to raise his head when he is laid on his stomach. At the age of three months, he leans on his elbow while lying down and can easily look from side to side. At the same time, he stands on his feet if he is held by his armpits. At the age of 8-8.5 months, he can sit, crawl and stand on his feet without the help of others. At the age of 12-13 months, the child can sit, stand, take a step without someone's help, that is, the child begins to walk. The child's inability to walk on time is caused by his poor health, the fact that he was sick a lot as a baby, and the late development of general movement and sensory organs.

In the first year of life, the development of the child's movements is very fast, the progress achieved in twelve months is amazing.

A child with limited limbs, a head, and a set of congenital general elementary movements, from a creature that practically needs help, turns into a small person, who not only stands easily on two legs, but also moves relatively freely and independently in the environment with the movement of the legs. at the same time, in space free from locomotion (functions that provide movement), he can perform complex manual control actions and actions designed to explore the surrounding world. A newborn does not have the ability to pay attention. It gradually develops involuntary attention under the influence of various stimuli. The smaller the scope of the child's imagination, the more intensive and continuous his attention to the familiar and new object for him. The mental effect of attention is known, it transforms the sensory complex into perception, enhances the transition of mental processes and helps keep images firmly in the memory.

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